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THE USE OF ENGLISH LOANWORDS IN THE FIELDS OF ANIMAL
HUSBANDRY AND MECHANIZATION IN AGRICULTURE

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Annotation. This article provides a linguistic and domain-specific analysis of anglicisms used in the animal husbandry and mechanization sectors of agriculture. Based on scientific sources, it examines the direct adoption of anglicisms into the Karakalpak language, their phonetic and grammatical adaptation, and their use alongside Karakalpak equivalents. The research findings help define strategies for the use of Anglicisms in the Karakalpak language.

Keywords: Anglicism, animal husbandry, mechanization, agricultural terminology, Karakalpak language.

Аннотация. В настоящей статье представлен лингвистический и отраслевой анализ англицизмов, используемых в таких секторах сельского хозяйства, как животноводство и механизация. На основе научных источников рассматриваются прямое заимствование англицизмов в каракалпакский язык, их фонетическая и грамматическая адаптация, а также их употребление наряду с каракалпакскими эквивалентами. Результаты исследования способствуют определению стратегий использования англицизмов в каракалпакском языке.

Ключевые слова: англицизм, животноводство, механизация, сельскохозяйственная терминология, каракалпакский язык.

Аннотация. Бу мақаллада аwil xojalıgınıń sharwashılıq hám mexanizaciyalastırıw sıyaqlı tarawlarında qollanılatusın anglicizmlerdiń lingvistikalıq hám tarawlıq analizi usınılǵan. Ilimiy derekler tiykarında anglicizmlerdiń qaraqalpaq tiline tikkeley ózlesiwı, olardıń fonetikalıq hám grammatikalıq beyimlesiwı, sonday-aq qaraqalpaq tilindegi ekvivalentleri menen qatar qollanıwı qarap shıǵıladı. Izertlew nátiyjeleri qaraqalpaq tilinde anglicizmlerdi qollanıw strategiyaların anıqlawǵa xızmet etedi.

Gilt sózler: anglicizm, sharwashılıq, mexanizaciyalastırıw, awil xojalıǵı terminologiyası, qaraqalpaq tili.

Introduction. In recent years, the process of globalization has formed a unified terminological space in the fields of science, technology, and production. Agriculture has not been excluded from this process. In particular, terms borrowed from English - Anglicisms - are widely used in the fields of animal husbandry and mechanization. This process supports the development of agricultural terminology in the Karakalpaq language and its application in scientific research [1].

Materials and methods. The process of adopting English words in animal husbandry and mechanization occurs in two main ways: the first is the direct adoption of the term without change, and the second is its use with phonetic or morphological

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adaptation. Additionally, some terms are used alongside Karakalpaq equivalents. This research is aimed at a systematic study of this process.

1. The use of anglicisms in the animal husbandry sector

In the field of animal husbandry, several Anglicisms have become firmly established as a result of advancements in breeding, feeding, and management systems.[2,3,4] For example:

- Breeding - násilshilik
- Feeding - azıqlandırırw
- Genetics - genetika
- Genomics - genomika
- Monitoring - monitoring/baqlaw
- Livestock management - sharwashılıqtı basqarıw

Although the term *breeding* is used in the Karakalpak language as *násilshilik*, its English version is also used in scientific texts. Similarly, the term *monitoring* is used in two different forms alongside the word *baqlaw*.

In the animal husbandry sector, English terms are often used without alteration in technical, scientific, and commercial texts, especially scientific terms such as *genetics* and *genomics*. In practical work, however, the terms *breeding* and *feeding* are used together with their Karakalpak equivalents.

Results. The Role of anglicisms in the field of mechanization

In the field of mechanization, Anglicisms are related to machinery, automation, and digital technologies. The most commonly used terms include:

- Traktor - unchanged
- Kombayın (combine) - unchanged
- Sensor - unchanged
- GPS - unchanged
- Precision agriculture - anıq diyqansılıq
- Smart farming - aqıllı awıl xojalıǵı

For example, *precision agriculture* (anıq diyqansılıq) and *smart farming* (aqıllı awıl xojalıǵı) are used as key concepts in modern mechanization [6]

In the field of technology and mechanization, English terms are used either unchanged or with phonetic-morphological adaptation. For example, *maintenance* → *texnikalıq xizmet* (technical service), *diagnostics* → *diagnostika*[7]

Discussion. Forms of anglicism usage in the Karakalpak Language

The use of anglicisms in the Karakalpak language occurs in three main forms:

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1. Used without change - *Traktor, Kombayn, Dron, Sensor, Genetics, Genomics [9]
2. Phonetic/morphological adaptation - *Management* → *menedjment*, *Marketing* → *marketing*, *Service* → *servis*, *Diagnostics* → *diagnostika*, *Technology* → *texnologiya*
3. Used with Karakalpak equivalents - *Feeding* → *Azıqlandırırw*, *Breeding* → *Násilshilik*, *Maintenance* → *Texnikalıq xizmet*[8]

Anglicisms in the Fields of Animal Husbandry and Mechanization

English Term | Karakalpak/Latin Form | Field | Usage Context

1 Breeding | Násilshilik | Animal Husbandry | Paired with equivalent

2 Feeding | Azıqlandırırw | Animal Husbandry | Paired with equivalent

3 Monitoring | Monitoring / Baqlaw | Animal Husbandry | Paired with equivalent

4 Genetics | Genetika | Animal Husbandry | Unchanged

5 Traktor | Traktor | Mechanization | Unchanged

6 Kombayn | Kombayn | Mechanization | Unchanged

7 Sensor | Sensor | Mechanization | Unchanged

8 Precision agriculture | Anıq diyqanshılıq | Mechanization | Translated

9 Smart farming | Aqıllı awıl xojalıǵı | Mechanization | Translated

10 Maintenance | Texnikalıq xizmet | Mechanization | Translated

Conclusion. The research shows that the use of anglicisms in the fields of animal husbandry and mechanization is directly linked to global scientific and technological development. Some terms are used without change, while others are used with phonetic-grammatical adaptation or alongside their Karakalpak equivalents. This process is important for the development and scientific grounding of agricultural terminology in the Karakalpak language.

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